

ADVANCED MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES FOR RTM INJECTION SURROGATE MODELING

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ABSTRACT

Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) is a widely adopted manufacturing technique for polymer matrix composites (PMCs), especially in aerospace and automotive sectors. However, accurate prediction of resin flow during the injection stage is computationally intensive, making real-time optimization unfeasible with conventional numerical solvers. This study proposes advanced deep learning-based surrogate models as a viable alternative to accelerate simulation and facilitate smart manufacturing. Specifically, it emphasizes the importance of architectural choices in surrogate modeling and presents a systematic comparison between two architectures: a fully convolutional encoder-decoder and a MIONet neural operator, both trained on synthetic datasets generated via OpenFOAM simulations.

The encoder-decoder model leverages densely connected convolutional layers to learn spatially structured mappings, while MIONet approximates nonlinear operators via coordinate-wise predictions using a dual-branch and trunk network formulation. Both models are evaluated on their ability to predict temporal evolutions of pressure and impregnation fields given information regarding the permeability field, the inlet pressure and the spatiotemporal coordinates. Two study cases, permeability fields with sharp and smooth permeability variations, are considered to account for different injection process disturbances. Results show that while both architectures demonstrate strong agreement with ground truth simulations, encoder-decoder model achieves higher predictive accuracy, particularly in capturing sharp resin fronts and local pressure gradients, as convolution-based inductive biases improve the fidelity of field reconstructions. Additionally, both models offer significant speedups, up to four orders of magnitude compared to OpenFOAM, highlighting the role of surrogate models as key enabling technologies for Digital Twin systems, which facilitate resilient and adaptive RTM Smart Manufacturing by enhancing the process's responsiveness to real-time disturbances.

1 INTRODUCTION

Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) is a cost-competitive manufacturing process for Polymer Matrix Composites (PMCs), suitable for large complex parts and large scales, and ideal for structural lightweight applications such as those required in aerospace and automotive industries. Its effectiveness is mainly related to the quality of resin impregnation in the fibers during injection, therefore, resin flow dynamics within the preform are modelled in early design stages to ensure an optimal injection strategy by using numerical filling simulations. However, inherent distortions to the manufacturing process usually arise, such as fiber misalignment, thickness variations and curvatures or mould gaps, being impractical to address real-time process optimization with numerical filling simulations because of their high computational and runtime demand. To overcome these drawbacks, surrogate modelling emerges as an alternative to numerical filling simulations, providing approximate

results in significantly reduced time with low computational cost associated. It allows real-time application, being one of the key enabling technologies for Digital Twins, essential to make the RTM manufacturing process resilient and insensitive to processing distortions towards Smart Manufacturing.

Data-driven surrogate models replicate complex physical processes by learning input–output relationships directly from data, usually collected from physical models or simulations, bypassing the need for explicit physical equations since they are assumed implicitly in data. In this context, Deep Learning (DL) models, a subset of Machine Learning, stand out due to their robustness and efficacy in handling complex, large-scale datasets. Among the various data-driven approaches, fully convolutional encoder-decoders [1] and neural operator-based models such as DeepONets [2], have gained significant popularity. In essence, if the learning task is viewed as a mapping from function-valued inputs, such as initial conditions, boundary conditions, or source terms, to function-valued outputs representing physical fields or system responses, both approaches aim to approximate the same underlying functional relationship, and the distinction, therefore, lies not in the nature of the learning task, but in the architectural choices that govern how data is processed and generalized. The architecture of a deep learning model plays a critical role in determining how effectively it captures patterns within complex datasets. It defines the pathway by which information flows from input to output, influencing both the model’s expressive capacity and its ability to generalize beyond the training distribution.

In this work, we conduct a systematic comparison between a fully convolutional encoder-decoder model and a MIONet architecture, a variant of DeepONet which includes two branch nets, employed as surrogate models for the RTM injection stage. The synthetic dataset generation process, including the two-phase fluid flow forward model and the dataset design, is described in Section 2. Section 3 details the architectures of both the convolutional encoder-decoder and the MIONet models, along with the training procedures. Section 4 presents a comparative analysis of the two approaches in terms of performance and inference time and finally, Section 5 outlines the key conclusions and reflects on their relevance for the optimization of the RTM process.

2 SYNTHETIC DATASET GENERATION

2.1 Two-phase fluid flow forward model

The flow of resin through porous media such as fiber preforms can be modeled by Darcy’s law, which links the average velocity of the fluid to the pressure gradient via a proportionality involving the material’s permeability and the fluid’s viscosity (1). Under the assumption of mass conservation, this relation leads to a pressure field equation that, together with proper boundary and initial conditions, allows the transient flow to be determined. As the liquid front progresses through the domain, the problem can be formulated as one with a moving boundary, where classical finite element methods can be used to iteratively resolve the pressure and velocity fields.

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \nabla p(\mathbf{x}, t) / \mu \quad (1)$$

In the context of resin injection processes, where two immiscible fluids such as resin and air interact, the interface evolution can be modeled using the Volume of Fluid (VOF) technique. This method introduces a variable denoted as α , which takes values between 0 and 1 to distinguish air ($\alpha = 0$) from resin ($\alpha = 1$). It is governed by the advection equation (2), allowing the interface to evolve consistently throughout the simulation. In this work, simulations were carried out using OpenFOAM, a widely used open-source platform for computational fluid dynamics. Specifically, the interFoam solver designed to simulate isothermal, incompressible two-phase flow using the VOF method, was employed.

$$d\alpha/dt + \nabla \cdot (\alpha \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

2.2 Dataset design

Simulations were run on a 96×96 structured mesh with a single cell of thickness created with Abaqus, assuming in-plane flow in the mould. The left wall of the domain was defined as an inlet, where a fixed pressure condition (3) was imposed, the right one was treated as a pressure outlet, with a fixed pressure of 0 bar, and the remaining ones were set as slip-free walls. Figure 1a) depicts the computational domain and boundary conditions employed.

$$p_{inlet} = p_0(1 - e^{-\gamma t}) \quad (3)$$

In order to account for process disturbances occurring during the injection stage, which lead to distinctive flow front deformations, two representative scenarios were considered: smooth and strong permeability variations. The first case represents the effects of fiber misalignment or non-uniform compaction, which result in an inhomogeneous flow front. It was modeled by sampling a Gaussian Random Field (GRF). The second case emulates the formation of preferential flow paths along the mould edges due to fiber gaps, where the resin advances faster. These channels, usually known as race-tracking, were modeled as regions of higher permeability compared to the bulk material ($\beta_{RT} = K/K_0$) [3]. Figure 1b) c) shows a permeability field example resulting from each disturbance scenario.

Figure 1: a) Computational domain and boundary conditions: inlet (left), outlet (right), and slip-free walls. A zoomed view of the structured mesh is highlighted. Permeability field with b) strong variations and c) smooth variations.

A diverse dataset of simulations was generated by sampling parameter tuples with Latin hypercube to ensure a uniform coverage of permeability and inlet pressure variations. Table 1 shows the range of the sampled parameters. The entire simulation pipeline, parameter generation, OpenFOAM configuration, execution, and output extraction, was automated via Python scripts and libraries such as PyFoam, Meshio and Gstools. A preprocessing step was carried out to non-dimensionalize the dataset, enabling the surrogate models to generalize to different process conditions, such as changes in resin viscosity, part scale, or maximum injection pressure (p_0), after being trained as long as they remain homothetic. Spatial coordinates were non-dimensionalized by the mold length L_0 , pressure values by the maximum applied pressure p_0 , and time by a characteristic filling time defined as $t_0 = \mu_0 L_0^2 / 2 K_0 p_0$ which represents the duration required to fill a mould of length L_0 when the flow occurs under steady conditions with constant viscosity μ_0 and bulk permeability K_0 . Data normalization was also applied to improve the training stability and convergence of the surrogate models.

γ (s^{-1})	β_{RT}	l_1 (mm)	l_2 (mm)
[0.002, 0.025]	[10, 100]	[5, 95]	[5, 95]

Table 1: Parameter ranges for synthetic dataset generation

3 ADVANCE DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES

3.1 Fully convolutional encoder-decoder

The fully convolutional encoder-decoder architecture employed in this work is the one proposed in [1]. This architecture employs a sequence of densely connected convolutional blocks [4], where each layer obtains inputs not only from the preceding layer but from all previous layers within the block, using $k=24$ as feature map growth rate. Transition layers follow each dense block to modulate feature map resolution via strided convolutions and deconvolutions in the encoder and decoder, respectively. The entire architecture contains approximately 3.5 M trainable parameters. An schematic overview is shown in Figure 2.

Its purpose is to represent high-dimensional input information by means of the encoder into a latent space of low dimensionality, to then reconstruct high-dimensional predictions via the decoder. Particularizing for the RTM process, the permeability field of the fibre preform (a 96×96 image) is encoded and then concatenated with gamma (γ), a pressure build-up parameter, and a time vector. In this way, the latent space contains all the key process information. After that, from this low dimensional latent space, data is reconstructed to predict fluid field and pressure fields over time (96×96 images) using two separated decoders.

Figure 2: Architectural overview of the fully convolutional encoder-decoder surrogate model [1].

3.2 MIONet

MIONet architecture consists of three interacting subnetworks: two branch networks that encode distinct input functions, and a trunk network that processes the spatial or temporal coordinates where predictions are to be made. The outputs of the branch and trunk networks are subsequently combined through an element-wise product followed by a sum to generate the final output function. Its purpose is to approximate nonlinear operators by learning mappings from function-valued inputs, such as initial conditions, boundary conditions, or source terms, to function-valued outputs corresponding to physical fields or system responses. In the context of the RTM process, the first branch network receives the permeability field as input, while the second branch network takes a discretized representation of the inlet pressure function, sampled at 25 time points. The trunk network, in turn, is provided with the spatial and temporal coordinates corresponding to the target prediction locations.

With respect to the backbone architectures of the branch and trunk networks, this study considers two MIONet configurations that differ in the implementation of the first branch network. The first configuration is the originally proposed in [5], named as Vanilla MIONet, which adopts fully connected neural networks (FNNs) for all three components, both branch networks and the trunk network. The second configuration remains the second branch and trunk networks fully connected, whereas the first branch network is replaced with a densely connected convolutional encoder identical to the one described in the previous section. To optimize the performance of both configurations, a systematic exploration of FNN hyperparameters was carried out by evaluating different combinations of network depth [2,4,6,8,10] and width [128,256,512,800,1024]. An schematic overview of the two proposed MIONet configurations is shown in Figure 3. Vanilla MIONet of width=6 and depth=800, with a total of approximately 17 M trainable parameters, achieved the best performance and is therefore adopted as the reference model for all subsequent comparisons in this study.

Figure 3: Overview of the MIONet configurations considered in this study. (a) Vanilla MIONet, composed entirely of fully connected networks. (b) MIONet variant incorporating a densely connected convolutional encoder as the first branch network.

3.3 Training

The training process was structured in two distinct phases: the first one focused on learning the pressure field and the second one, the impregnation field. To ensure a fair and rigorous comparison between the encoder-decoder and MIONet architectures, multiple training configurations were systematically evaluated to determine the most effective setup for each model. This included variations in regularization strategies (with or without batch normalization), optimization algorithms (SGD, Adam, L-BFGS, and NNCG), and loss functions (MAE, MSE and $L_{n-\log}$ composite loss).

During the first training stage, a $L_{n-\log}$ composite loss function was employed. This loss function combines power and logarithmic terms in a piecewise manner to enhance convergence in scenarios where residuals exhibit a bimodal distribution, an aspect commonly encountered in dual-phase flow simulations. Additional information regarding this loss function can be found in [1]. Normalization

was applied through batch normalization, weights were initialized using He initialization and ReLU was used as activation function. The Adam optimizer was used in combination with a learning rate scheduling strategy based on the ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler. The initial learning rates were set to 0.01 for the encoder-decoder model and 0.001 for MIONet. Patience values of 20 and 50,000 iterations were configured respectively for learning rate reduction, with a decay factor of 0.1. To prevent undertraining due to time constraints, early stopping was implemented with patience values of 60 and 100,000 iterations, and the maximum number of training epochs was set to 500 and 250,000 for the encoder-decoder and MIONet models, respectively. Overall, training times were approximately 3 hours for the encoder-decoder and 2 days and 7 hours for MIONet.

The second training phase was carried out differently for the encoder-decoder and MIONet architectures. For the encoder-decoder, the prediction of the impregnation field was formulated as a binary classification task, distinguishing resin (1) from air (0), and trained using the binary cross-entropy (BCE) loss function. In contrast, due to the design of DeepONet, in which the outputs of the branch and trunk networks are combined via an inner product, the model cannot guarantee output values constrained to the $[0, 1]$ interval. This structural limitation renders a binary classification approach unsuitable for MIONet. To address this, the impregnation field for MIONet was modeled as a level-set function, a continuous scalar field where the resin-air interface (flow front) is identified by a sharp gradient. This level-set representation was constructed using information from the pressure field, leveraging the physical correlation between pressure gradients and flow front propagation in RTM processes. As such, the task was reformulated as a regression problem, and the $L_{n-\log}$ composite loss function was employed to guide training. After inference, the predicted impregnation field was thresholded to obtain a binary mask, enabling a direct comparison with the encoder-decoder output. All remaining training settings were kept consistent with those described previously. The total training duration was approximately 3 hours for the encoder-decoder and 2 days and 10 hours for MIONet.

4 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Figure 3 and Figure 4 illustrate the predictive performance of both the encoder-decoder and MIONet surrogate models for resin impregnation and pressure field across different time steps, using two representative permeability cases with strong variations and smooth variations, respectively. Both models exhibit high agreement with the target fields, successfully capturing the global behavior of the impregnation and pressure distributions. Among the two models, the encoder-decoder exhibits greater predictive accuracy, particularly in tracking the advancing resin front and capturing the spatial pressure gradients across the domain. MIONet, while successfully reproducing the overall flow behavior, presents slightly larger deviations. This is due to the encoder-decoder processes the entire input field as a structured image, preserving spatial locality through convolutions and hierarchical feature extraction, which enables the model to capture fine-grained spatial patterns, such as sharp interfaces at the resin front and local pressure gradients. In contrast, MIONet operates on coordinate-wise predictions, evaluating the output at individual spatial points without modeling the global structure of the output field, as each prediction is made independently of its neighbors.

From a computational standpoint, Table 2 demonstrates that both surrogate models achieve a substantial reduction in simulation time, decreasing inference time by several orders of magnitude compared to traditional OpenFOAM solvers. While the encoder-decoder achieves predictions in just 12 ms and MIONet in 83 ms, conventional simulations require nearly 4 minutes per case. This drastic improvement in computational efficiency highlights the potential of both approaches for accelerating resin transfer molding simulations. In particular, their speed and responsiveness make them strong candidates for real-time simulation and control applications within manufacturing environments.

Figure 4: Surrogate models' predictions for a permeability field with strong variations. a) Spatial distribution of the permeability field. b) Temporal evolution of the resin impregnation field (left) and pressure field (right) at selected time steps. Rows correspond to the ground truth (OpenFOAM), predictions from MIONet and encoder–decoder (E–D) models, and their respective error maps.

Figure 5: Surrogate models' predictions for a permeability field with smooth variations. a) Spatial distribution of the permeability field. b) Temporal evolution of the resin impregnation field (left) and pressure field (right) at selected time steps. Rows correspond to the ground truth (OpenFOAM), predictions from MIONet and encoder–decoder (E–D) models, and their respective error maps.

	ED	MIONet	OpenFOAM
Inference time	12 ms	83 ms	3.95 min

Table 2: Execution time comparison

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work has investigated and compared the performance of two advanced deep learning architectures, fully convolutional encoder-decoder and MIONet, as surrogate models for the RTM injection stage. Two representative scenarios were addressed to reflect inherent disturbances that appear during the RTM injection: one involving sharp heterogeneities in the permeability field and another representing smooth heterogeneities in the permeability field. By analyzing their predictive performance on the estimation of the impregnation and pressure fields over time, the study provides valuable insights into the trade-offs between spatially structured models and operator-learning frameworks in simulating two-phase flow dynamics during resin injection. While both architectures capture the global flow dynamics and pressure distributions with high fidelity, the encoder-decoder consistently outperforms MIONet in predictive accuracy, particularly for sharp resin fronts and spatial pressure gradients, due to its ability to leverage spatial inductive biases through convolutional processing. These findings underscore the critical importance of architectural design in deep learning-based surrogate modeling. Moreover, both models significantly accelerate simulation time, achieving speedups of several orders of magnitude over conventional solvers. This real-time execution enables their integration into Digital Twin frameworks for Smart Manufacturing, facilitating real-time process monitoring and control to make the manufacturing process more robust and resilient to unexpected disturbances that naturally arise during operation.

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